

GDP Growth Rate and Labor Force Participation in the Italian Economy

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The analysis of data on the Italian labor market over the period 2004-2024 highlights significant dynamics among employees, permanent, fixed-term and self-employed workers. These trends reflect the structural changes in the economy, the impact of labor policies and the challenges related to economic and pandemic crises. The overall number of employees is constantly increasing, from around 16 million in 2004 to almost 19 million in 2024. This growth is largely driven by permanent employees, who show a positive trend, especially from 2016 onwards. However, a progressive increase in fixed-term contracts is also noted, which represent a growing share of the labor market. This data points to an increase in labor flexibility, probably linked to labor market reforms and the needs of companies to adapt to uncertain economic contexts. Temporary workers increased significantly in the period analyzed, from around 1.8 million in 2004 to over 3 million in 2022-2023. This increase reflects a greater precariousness of work, with a peak between 2017 and 2023. This can be attributed to the economic crisis of 2008-2014 and the pandemic, which pushed many companies to prefer temporary contracts to manage economic uncertainty. The number of self-employed workers shows a decreasing trend. In 2004, they stood at around 6.2 million, while in 2024 they fell to just over 5 million. This decline reflects a structural transformation of the Italian economy, with a reduction in traditional small businesses and an increase in larger, employee-oriented companies. Furthermore, increasing digitalization and automation have reduced the need for independent labor in some sectors. The effects of the economic crises are evident in the data. The 2008-2014 global financial crisis led to a stagnation in the number of permanent employees and an increase in fixed-term contracts. The 2020 pandemic caused a temporary reduction in employment, with a sharp recovery from 2021, driven by both permanent employees and a slight increase in fixed-term contracts. The data highlight an increasingly polarized labor market between stability (permanent employees) and flexibility (fixed-term), with a constant reduction in the weight of self-employed workers. Future policies should focus on promoting job security and enhancing self-employment to respond to the ongoing economic transformations.

The data show a clear decrease in inactivity in the long term. In 2004, the number of inactive people stood at around 14.3 million, while in 2024 it fell to around 12.5 million. This trend suggests a progressive reduction in inactivity, probably linked to policies aimed at encouraging participation in the labor market, improving employment opportunities and an increase in female participation in the labor market. During the global financial crisis of 2008-2009, a significant increase in the number of inactive people is observed, reaching a peak of around 14.9 million in September 2009. This increase reflects the economic difficulties of that period, which led to a temporary exit from the labor market for many individuals. Subsequently, starting from 2010, the numbers stabilized, with an initial decrease from 2011. The 2020 pandemic temporarily interrupted the downward trend of inactive people. A sharp increase is observed in March 2020 (14 million) and an even sharper peak in April 2020 (14.6 million). This phenomenon can be attributed to the lockdowns and restrictions that reduced labor market participation, forcing many workers to temporarily withdraw. From 2021 onwards, a strong recovery is observed with a steady reduction in inactive people. This trend highlights the success of the economic and labor market recovery measures adopted after the pandemic. By 2024, the number of inactive people falls to the lowest levels of the entire period analyzed, highlighting greater inclusion in the labor market. The data show slight seasonal variations in the number of inactive people. For example, the summer months often record slightly higher peaks, probably due to reduced activity in some work sectors during the holidays. The overall trend suggests an improvement in economic and employment conditions in Italy, with a progressive reduction in inactivity. However, it remains essential to implement policies that further foster labor inclusion, especially for the weakest groups, such as young people, women and senior workers, to consolidate the progress achieved.

GDP and Labor Force Participation Rate growth rate. The correlation coefficient between the GDP growth rate and the Labor Force Participation Rate (LFPR) change rate is -0.198, indicating a weak negative relationship between the two variables. In general, the two indicators do not appear to be closely related and can move in opposite directions in certain periods. The GDP growth rate has shown strong volatility over the period analyzed, with significant fluctuations. Growth was positive in the early 1990s, followed by a sharp decline in 2009 (-5.28%) during the global financial crisis. A rapid recovery occurred in 2010 (+1.71%), but the most noticeable collapse occurred in 2020 (-8.97%) due to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, 2021 saw a significant rebound, with a growth rate of 8.31%, the highest value of the entire period analyzed. The rate of change of the LFPR shows less marked variations than GDP, maintaining greater stability. Positive signs are observed in the early 2000s, with constant increases in labor participation. However, 2020 marked a significant decline (-2.47%), reflecting the impact of the pandemic also on the labor force. In 2021, there is a moderate recovery (+0.39%) and a further recovery in 2022 (+1.67%). The weak correlation between the variables suggests that the factors influencing economic growth and labor participation may be

independent or respond to different dynamics. During the economic crises of 2009 and 2020, both indicators suffered significant declines, highlighting how recessions have a simultaneous impact on GDP and labor participation. However, in periods of economic growth, the LFPR does not always follow the same pace as GDP, suggesting that factors such as demography and labor policies play a crucial role. The average value of the GDP growth rate between 1991 and 2022 was 0.75%. The distribution of the GDP growth rate shows a concentration around values close to zero, with some extreme positive and negative peaks, a sign of the economic volatility recorded during the period.

Sources:

Istat <https://www.istat.it/comunicato-stampa/occupati-e-disoccupati-dati-provvisori-aprile-2024/>

World Bank <https://data.worldbank.org/country/italy>

References

Arnone, M., Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2024). Banking Stability in the ESG Framework Across Italian Regions (No. 121452). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Arnone, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The People You Can Count on in the Italian Regions* (No. 121277). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Resta, E., Logroscino, G., Tafuri, S., Peter, P., Noviello, C., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Mental Health Index across the Italian Regions in the ESG Context* (No. 3cztm). Center for Open Science.

Arnone, M., Angelillis, B., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *Graduates, Training and Employment Across the Italian Regions* (No. 121117). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions* (No. 120637). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions* (No. 120603). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions* (No. 120550). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A. (2024). The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions. *Available at SSRN 4771132*.

Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions* (No. 120542). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Resta, E., & Costantiello, A. (2024). *The Renunciation of Healthcare Services in the Italian Regions in the ESG Context* (No. 120351). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Resta, O., Resta, E., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). *Elderly People Treated in Integrated Home Care in Italian Regions: A Metric Approach* (No. 119621). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Resta, E., Resta, O., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). *Investigating the Determinants of Beds for High-Care Specialties in the Italian Regions in the Environmental, Social and Governance Model* (No. 119622). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Leogrande, D., & Anobile, F. (2023). *Beds in Health Facilities in the Italian Regions: A Socio-Economic Approach* (No. 9sjcr). Center for Open Science.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, D. (2023). The Socio-Economic Determinants Of The Number Of Physicians In Italian Regions (No. 92wnh). Center for Open Science.